

Job satisfaction of Iranian physiotherapists in 1387.

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Abstract

Background: Job satisfaction is defined as the viewpoint of a person and the collection of positive thoughts about his job. In the other word, job satisfaction is affected by salary, interconnections and etc. Job satisfaction of physiotherapists has never been investigated precisely in Iran so the aim of this study was to evaluate the job satisfaction of Iranian physiotherapists. Methods: 102 physiotherapists attended in the annual congress of physical therapy participated in this study and filled the "Sternberg" job satisfaction form. This test comprised of 30 questions. Except the twelfth and thirteen's questions other questions have three items and items are graded to one, three or five according to the question. Higher grade indicates more job satisfaction. SPSS software was used to analyze the data. Results: Results showed that 81.4% of physiotherapists had an average satisfaction, 15.7% had low satisfaction and 2% had very low job satisfaction scores. Our test range was between 39 and 122 and showed that none of the 102 participants had a high job satisfaction. Conclusion: Complete independence in managing the patients is one of the satisfaction reasons for the physiotherapists all round the world and physical and mental stress is a reason for unsatisfaction. It is suggested that job satisfaction need to be evaluated every six months to study the changes occur.

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